

**ASSESSING EMPLOYEES' MOTIVATION IN TERTIARY
EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN SIERRA LEONE: INSTITUTION
OF ADVANCED MANAGEMENT AND TECHNOLOGY (IAMTECH)
AND NJALA UNIVERSITY (NU), SIERRA LEONE**

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Abstract:

Employee motivation is a key element that subsequently achieve organizational blueprint in modern day of organizational operations. On this ground, the researchers assess employees' motivation in tertiary educational institutions in Sierra Leone. It covers the Institute of Advanced Management and Technology (IAMTECH) and its affiliate institution, Njala University (NU). Differences were drawn between these two institutions, as IAMTECH is private and NU public. Motivation is necessary for effective and efficient organizational dynamism such as room for growth, development, health work environment, feeling of belonging, and achievement of organizational objectives. Motivated employees dedicate their energies and skills to their jobs, thereby implementing and attaining the organizational policies and blueprints. This enhances workplace ethics and accelerates employee motivation and performance in tertiary educational institutions in Sierra Leone. It clearly states that motivation is not only giving financial incentives and rewards, but also makes employees' feel as if they are part of the organization success. It is evident in the research that, applying effective employees' motivation either moral or financial helps achieve organizational objectives in both public and private sectors in Sierra Leone. However, there are some constrains in achieving the ultimate goal of the research, as most heads and decision makers in these institutions lack the required skills to motivate employees' performance in this 19th century culturally society in the west coast of Africa. Therefore, the researchers created room for more innovative techniques that will definitely yield maximal employees' motivation in tertiary educational institutions in Sierra Leone.

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1. Introduction

The emergence of several new educational institutions in Sierra Leone, like University of Makeni, Ernest Bai Koroma University, the Canadian College at Mile 91, Limkokwing University of Creative Technology and several others, are meant with tough competition for the plus seven million population. The traditional universities such as, Fourah bay College, Njala University, Institute of Public Administration and Management, and College of Allied Health Sciences have larger student population and staff. This increases in tertiary educational institutions demands effective employees' motivational skills and techniques that will subsequently enhance job performance in the two research institutions. Motivation ensures that an individual employee put more energy and effort (internal and external) at workplace [1]. Reeve in 2001 stated that, motivation is derived from either intrinsic or extrinsic behavior. Intrinsic is achieving self-competency and curiosity internally at work environment, and learning new skills externally to be implemented at workplace is referred to as an extrinsic behavior [2].

Employees' motivation is critical for any organization success. When employees are highly motivated, they tend to deliver quality work that meets the needs of the nation. Motivation is a tool to attain standard performance in tertiary educational institutions with regards to academic and administrative staff determines the quality of students produced. Private educational institutions derive funds only from student fees projects, and good wishers. This warrants student tuition to cover all the expenses. Unlike state controlled universities, fees are subsidized by the central government, resulting to lower students' tuition fees. Unfortunately, this is opposite at IAMTECH, where students pay much lower tuition compared to the public universities. This is to ensure that education is available to all. More incentives, rewards, bonuses, seminars, workshops, training, and good working relationship definitely result to effective employees' motivation that will lead to higher employees' performance.

2. Statement of the Problem

Majority of lecturers in Sierra Leone are poorly paid compared to other sector in the workforce. This is evident as several universities have experienced numerous strike actions, for instance most recently at Njala University, Limkokwing University of Creative Technology and many others. These strikes affected about 45 percent of the country's student population in 2015-2016, and 2016 - 2017 academic years. The major findings of the research was attributed to low salaries, biased promotions based on political and connectocracy, bad leadership, and variety of workload, discipline among students and academic staff, working among colleagues with low educational status,

and un-conducive work environment. A world Bank Report in 2004, suggested that about 23,000 qualified academic professional seek for greener pasture out of Africa each year for better condition of services. It is estimated that most Sierra Leonean who studied abroad failed to return to contribute positively towards improving high quality of education, because of poor condition of services in this postwar country. This heavily affects academic performance among academic staff, thereby translating into poor student's academic performance.

2.1 Purpose of Research

This research is carried out to assess employees' motivation in tertiary educational institutions: IAMTECH and Njala University. The researchers examine the reason as to what determinant factor will achieve effective motivation strategies in these institutions, and provide suggestions or recommendations to senior management.

3. Literature Review

Work output heavily depends on the talent and skills of employees' inner insight. Garbage in, garbage out, meaning having workforce with low IQ, result to poor result. Therefore, if such employee lacks the necessary God given skills and talent, or unable to acquire it through job training/seminar/workshop to perform a particular task, then the organization is doom to fail. Moreover, in a scenario where the employee has all these ingredients along with adequate job motivation, optimal job performance will be achieved. In [3], referred to motivation as the willingness to influence a high level of effort to attain organizational goals, stigmatized by the efforts and abilities to satisfy. They categorically viewed motivation as: organizational goals, needs and efforts. Motivation in this content is the inner force that prompts individuals to achieve personal and organizational blueprint.

Cultivating innovative motivational techniques to meet the present day needs of tertiary educational institutions is paramount, as a result of numerous changes within modern institutions. Organizations spirit comes from the motivation of its employees, weather the company is public or private [4]. Motivation is a driving vehicle for employees' performance in an organization. Employee motivation is one of the strategies any successful administrators can use to achieve higher job performance among the workforce in an organization. A motivated employee always apply maximum energy to attain the organization blueprint, and un-motivated employee on the other hand, feel as if they have being neglected and left behind, resulting to low input into their job. Theoretically, employee motivation is straightforward but at the same time hard to evaluate empirically. Furthermore, motivated employees technically contribute greatly to achieve the organizational blueprint, and therefore, should be seeing as an important asset in tertiary educational institutions, allowing the input of human resources to be maximized in regard to fulfilling the potential output expected.

Employee motivation is an essential element in public and private tertiary educational institutions, with regards to either the employee is skilled or unskilled, and / or professionals. It is a huge challenge in this competitive today's global workspace to actively motivate employee, so as to win more skilled and innovative workforce in an organization. Effective employees' motivation can achieve higher job fulfillment in an organization, benefiting both the employer and employees. Therefore, it is vital for tertiary educational institutions to implement innovative motivational techniques to meet the diverse needs of the organization.

Abraham Maslow in 1954 indicated the factors that motivate human beings, suggesting that we all have the same type of needs arranged in a hierarchical order. Another great author Frederick Herzberg, in the 1950s conducted an extensive research focusing on motivation. He indicated that two sets of factors: motivators and hygiene factors, are both paramount to motivate employees, but with different reasons. Maslow's hierarchy of needs and Herzberg's two-factor theory are widely known theories of motivation. Importantly, these theories failed to explain why and how motivation develops or is sustained over time. Modern CEOs and managers have developed more dynamic models: Equity Theory, Expectancy Theory and Goal-Setting Theory to achieve organizational blueprint.

4. Staff Motivation at IAMTECH

IAMTECH being a private tertiary educational institution in Sierra Leone work hard to implement effective motivation, even though there is no financial support from the central government. Education is the overall development of an individual in all ramifications and not limited to classroom jurisdiction [5]. It must ensure that generational core values and knowledge are sustained. With the meager student tuition fees, IAMTECH still succeeded to motivates its employees by assigning top management positions to the young talented and educated employees, providing seminars/training/workshops either internally or externally to dedicated and hardworking staff, provision of scholarship to promising academic staff, and aid staff financially and morally in time of need.

Academic staff play important role in achieving high quality tertiary education. Several researches have being carried out on teachers' motivation exploring different schemes that can attain maximal job satisfaction in higher educational institutions development [6]. A research conducted in Nigeria concluded that academic staff spent 48 percent on administrative tasks, and only 29 percent on teaching [7]. This is also visible at IAMTECH, with senior management given more job assignments, totaling about 45 percent being spent on administrative functions, and 40 percent on teaching. The poor salary rate at IAMTECH is a major setback in staff motivation, leading to mass exodus of qualified and hardworking staff to seek employment in public universities

across the country with huge pay differences. This demerit prompts academic staff to engage in part time job to supplement their monthly salaries.

Financial reward is not the only factor that influence staff motivation, but a combination of both tangible and intangible factors. Money works best if the employee is recognized empowered, supported, and takes part in decision making with feedbacks are the primary motivators for workers inspiration to perform their functions effectively. Motivation is crucial for future success and performance of any tertiary educational institutions [8].

Furthermore, enhance job training can be utilized to achieve successful motivation for employees' development [9]. Therefore, educational institutions must provide feedback to its employees in order for communication to flow among employees [10].

5. Methodology

The research focuses on the motivational strategies deployed by IAMTECH to achieve its organizational blueprint. Therefore, the research targeted a sample population of all senior management; both academic and administrative staff at IAMTECH.

5.1 Sample Size and Research Instruments

The research utilizes the nine departments in the two schools. 60 participants were involved in the research; 45 academic staff and 15 administrative staff respectively using random sampling method. The data collected were confidential and authentic in nature. Questionnaires were distributed to all the respondents and later feedbacks were sent to the researchers to compile and summarize the results.

5.2 Data Collection and Source of Data

Data used in this research was sourced from both primary and secondary sources. Primary data source was obtained from the questionnaire distributed among the selected respondents at IAMTECH and Njala University. The secondary sources of data were sourced from online, books, articles, journal, reports, theses and other important academic materials related to the topic in question.

5.3 Challenges Faced during the Research

Much difficulty was faced especially traveling to Njala Mooned campus and Njala Bo campus to collect the required data for analysis, about 2 - 3 hours drive. Moreover, some respondent fear of being victimized if they reveal the real situation on the ground. Despite the survey being anonymous, respondents fear as it details information about their departments. This was inevitable, as the study tries to assess employees' motivation I tertiary educational institutions in Sierra Leone.

5.4 Background to the Research Institution

IAMTECH, an emerging tertiary educational institution in Sierra Leone established during the 1991 bloody civil war, and is owned by indigenous Sierra Leonean situated in the heart of the capital city Freetown. It is termed as the Silicon Valley of Sierra Leone with technology as the main pillar of education. As a private institution, it is trying hard to implement new innovative motivational strategies to win the heart of the greater student population.

6. Result and Findings

Table 1 indicates employees' level of satisfaction between the two educational institutions.

Table 1: Employees' Level of Satisfaction

Institution	Determinant	Percentage (%)
IAMTECH	Highly Satisfied	12.04
	Satisfied	21.06
	Average	30.00
	Dissatisfied	25.90
	Not Sure	11.00
Njala University	Highly Satisfied	45.00
	Satisfied	30.00
	Average	20.90
	Dissatisfied	2.10
	Not Sure	3.00

Table 1 indicates that employees' level of satisfaction is based on the nature of the institution standing. Private institution normally source fund mainly from student tuition fee, as opposed to public institution getting sponsorship from the central government. 12.04% are highly satisfied compared to 45.00% at Njala University. This further indicates that the income capability determines the level of satisfaction. Moreover, employees at IAMTECH are more dissatisfied than at Njala University, 25.90 % and 2.00 % respectively due the condition of services.

Table 2: Motivational Level of Staff at IAMTECH and NU

Institution	Determinant	Percentages (%)
IAMTECH	Strongly Agree	20.00
	Agree	60.00
	Neither Agree nor Disagree	15.20
	Disagree	5.80
Njala University	Strongly Agree	50.04
	Agree	40.06
	Neither Agree nor Disagree	6.90
	Disagree	3.00

Table 2 shows that the staff at Njala University strongly agreed about 50.04 % compared to 20.00 % at IAMTECH. Fortunately, for IAMTECH as a private institution, it has more dedicated and committed staff worked tirelessly 24/7 round the clock to ensure that all the departments fulfill their daily job obligations. Unlike at NU whose employees have another job elsewhere, thereby resulting to poor job performance.

Table 3: Employees Motivational Factors

Institution	Motivational Factors	Percentages (%)
IAMTECH	Recognition	21.10
	Job Feature	10.10
	Job Appreciation	13.80
	Salary Increment	5.40
	Seminar/Workshop/Training	30.80
	Scholarship	12.20
	Rewards	7.00
	Level on Duty	2.60
Njala University	Recognition	45.00
	Job Feature	10.00
	Job Appreciation	20.00
	Salary Increment	14.00
	Seminar/Workshop/Training	8.00
	Scholarship	10.00
	Rewards	5.00
	Level on Duty	8.00

Table 3 indicates that IAMTECH having less staff population as compared to Njala University makes it easier to manage. In terms of staff salary incentives and increment, Njala University stands on a better footing than IAMTECH, as their salaries are being subsidized by the state. And unlike IAMTECH, which pays staff salaries from the meager student fees as the only source of income. Nevertheless, IAMTECH provides more scholarship packages to its academic staff than Njala University. About 12.20 % and 10.00 % scholarships are being provided by IAMTECH and Njala University respectively on an annual basis. Also, about 30.80 % and 8.00 % of staff are being financed to attend seminars and training abroad from IAMTECH and Njala University respectively; a goodwill gesture provided the People's Republic of China throughout the year. This has motivated more staff to focus their attention to achieve the organizational blueprint. Notably, state controlled tertiary educational institutions refer compliance and not performance based, but private institution follows both compliance and performance metric for its daily operations.

Table 4a: Employees Motivational Strategies adopted
 by Senior Management at IAMTECH

Statements	S.A	%	A	%	S.D	%	D	%
Does management pay staff salary on time?	9	90	1	10	-	-	-	-
Does the institution provide soft loan facility to dedicated staff?	4	40	4	40	2	20	-	-
Does senior management involve their staff in making managerial decisions?	2	20	5	50	2	20	1	10
Does the senior management consider teamwork as an important organizational asset?	7	70	3	30	-	-	-	-
Does the senior management acknowledge staff personal achievements?	3	30	2	20	4	40	1	10
Is there any mutual relationship between top management and the entire staff?	5	50	4	40	1	10	-	-
Does the senior management provide professional growth for staff such as staff capacity training, and research?	6	60	2	20	1	10	1	10
Are annual awards giving to well deserving staff frequently?	3	30	2	20	3	30	2	20
Are staff promotions on merit basis?	2	20	2	20	3	20	3	30

Table 4b: Employees Motivational Strategies adopted
 by Senior Management at Njala University

Statements	S.A	%	A	%	S.D	%	D	%
Does management pay staff salary on time?	5	50	5	50	-	-	-	-
Does the institution provide soft loan facility to dedicated staff?	2	20	3	30	3	30	2	20
Does senior management involve their staff in making managerial decisions?	8	80	2	20	-	-	-	-
Does the senior management consider teamwork as an important organizational asset?	5	50	5	50	-	-	-	-
Does the senior management acknowledge staff personal achievements?	6	60	2	20	1	10	1	10
Is there any mutual relationship between top management and the entire staff?	3	30	4	40	2	20	1	10
Does the senior management provide professional growth among the staff such as staff capacity training, and research?	7	70	2	20	1	10	-	-
Are annual awards giving to well deserving staff frequently?	4	40	5	50	1	10	-	-
Are staff promotions on merit basis?	7	70	2	20	1	10	-	-

Table 4a shows employees motivational strategies adopted by senior management and IAMTECH. It indicates 90% of the staff said that management paid their salary on time and 10% agreed on the evaluation metric. In the soft loan column, 40 % strongly agreed, 40 % also agreed and 20 % disagreed. Teamwork accounts about 70 % of staff strongly agreeing its applicability and 30 % also agreed. Only 30 % of staff said that they are given annual awards as a form of motivation compared to 20 % agreeing. And finally, staff promotion scored the least, about 20 % strongly agreeing and 30 % disagreeing.

Table 4b shows employees strategies adopted by senior management at Njala University. The research reveals that only 20 % strongly agreed that their salaries are

paid on time and 30 % disagreed. About 70 % acknowledged that staff development initiative is on the increase, and only 10 % disagreed. 70 % said that the university senate and court determine staff promotions.

7. Discussion

The research indicates that senior management and departmental heads are the main pillars of motivation [11]. A new innovative approach for organizational success is lecturer motivation as stated by Lee and Yu. IAMTECH management usually motivates their employees in different forms: rewards, incentives, promotions, scholarship, seminars/training, and soft loans that are intrinsic in nature [12]. He viewed reward as a tangible and that employees should work for it before such facility is accorded to him/her.

However, though IAMTECH is a private tertiary educational institution with limited source of income, it still proves to have achieved its organizational blueprint. Young qualified employees are normally assigned impressive nomenclatures that motivate them to exert more energy on their job. It is stated that the relevant physical facilities cannot be neglected [13]. The research indicated that institutional facilities greatly improved on job performance at IAMTECH. The participation of heads of departments and senior lecturers by the two deans produces sound decision for the institution.

However, a research in 2000 and 2002 respectively indicated that there are other underlying factors: social status, leadership approach, and management style if poorly managed undermine lecturers' output towards their jobs. Democratic style of leadership is much more preferable than the autocratic leadership style. This makes employees feel as if they are recognized and appreciated for their input into the success of the organizations' success. The research also indicated that providing seminars and training to employees especially outside the country motivate them more. Frederic Taylor scientific approach to management, suggested that majority of the heads of departments use human-relation scheme that is staff centered in nature.

The study further indicates that performance of lecturers is attained if they are encouraged to be creative and innovative. Dedicated staff is more motivated if they are better appreciated for their role in enhancing the organizational standards. It also reveals that maximal cooperation's among the workforce help to achieve better working environment. The open door policy of the chief executive officer and other top management achieved better work environment.

8. Conclusions

The research indicated that, not only financial rewards motivate employees, but also recognition and moral support. Making employees to participate in the decision-

making process produce optimal willingness to do more for the organization. Staff capacity development schemes require regular review to meet the needs of the present workforce talent and skill. Provision of bonuses serves as a motivational factor for employees' performance, but must be commensurate with the work done, with an upward adjustment.

Career advancement and promotion achieve optimal goal, and ensure that those motivated employees become more dedicated to the affairs of the institution they see as their property. Interpersonal interaction among senior management and staff is imminent for any modern organization success. Granting opportunities to dedicated employees motivate others to follow the footpath of their colleagues. Attending seminars and training externally, especially abroad enhance job performance and those skills and knowledge gained during the process help build a better tertiary educational institution that produces high quality of education among the general student population in Sierra Leone. Fortunately, all the respondents currently work at the selected institutions. This makes the process much more transparent and genuine.

From the research findings, the researchers indicated that additional task plays essential part in creating employee's character and their working routine. Neutrality and unbiased nature of successful administrators wins the heart of the working force in an organization. A well-disciplined and democratic leadership style with everyone in the organization works as a team to achieve the objective of the organization. Managers should pay maximum attention and care to their employees, and subsequently motivate their employee towards their individual tasks.

The success of any organization depends on how its employees are motivated, producing the actual expectations. Normally, wages can also de-motivate an employee. Although, several researches identified wages as a motivating factor, but what actually motivates employees are different and distinct. The effectiveness of either private or public educational institution depends upon the motivation of their employees. Knowing what motivates employees and incorporating this knowledge into the reward system subsequently helps both IAMTECH and NU to identify, recruit, employ, train, and retain a productive workforce. Motivating employees necessarily requires effective coordination between employers and employees. Employee actually revealing what best motivate them is good for IAMTECH and NU, and managers should be willing to design and implement a better reward scheme that eventually motivate employees at the selected institutions.

The research indicates that extrinsic motivation notably salary increment is better appreciated by the employees to meet the daily expenses. But recognition, appreciation and job feature are much more preferable than financial gain in higher educational institution. The findings will surely help top management of the selected institutions to effectively implement innovative employees' motivation.

9. Recommendation

The researchers forwarded the following recommendations based on their findings as:

- Top management should always encourage a cohesive teamwork among colleague workers.
- Top management should always motivate their employees by providing rewards, incentives, and salary increment, but also learn to recognizes, and appreciates their employees for the success.
- Staff capacity development should be routinely carried out to increase the knowledge and awareness relevant skills necessarily to produce optimal work output.
- Institutional facilities should ensure that effective teaching platform is provided to meet the needs of the modern technological setting thereby improving academic excellence. Managers should continually establish cordial atmosphere with their academic staff to promote enhance performance.
- Employees should be involved in the decision making process to promote excellent performance, and continue to create a pleasant working environment to enhance job performance.
- Top management should allow employees to utilize their God given talent, but in accordance with the goals of the institution.
- Prompt payment of academic staff salary, remunerations and allowances on time motivates employees to attain high job performance.
- Democratic style of leadership permits employees to perform their duties diligently, and subsequently produces the expected outcomes of the organizational blueprint. Universities and other tertiary educational institutions should adopt a good leadership scheme to solve problems. Annual award ceremony to acknowledge employees achievement result to a better motivational scheme.

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